

The Influence of Animated Film Media on the Independence of Group B Children Aged 5-6 Years At TK Prestige Bilingual School

Cindy Syachrani Fauziah*, Kamtini²
State University of Medan

Corresponding Author: Cindy Syachrani Fauziah cindysyachranif@gmail.com

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Early Childhood,
Animation Films,
Independence of Children
Aged 5-6 Years

Received: 22, August
Revised: 20, September
Accepted: 25, October

©2023 Fauziah, Kamtini:
This is an open-access article
distributed under the terms
of the [Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the results of children's independence through the use of animated film media in group B children at TK Prestige Bilingual School. The results of this research were that the average score given the animated film treatment was 10.53 in the very good category, while the average score not treated with the animated film was 9.13 in the very good category. From the score statement, the data shows that learning activities using animated films can increase the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School. This can be proven by obtaining scores given treatment and no treatment. Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it shows that there is a significant influence from the use of animated film media on the independence of group B children, and from the results of the t-test, it is obtained that $t_{count} < t_{table}$, namely $0.000 < 0.05$ at the level $\alpha = 0.005$ with the results of the t-test it can be concluded that There is a significant influence from the use of animated film media on the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School.

INTRODUCTION

All individuals have the same right to receive a high standard of education, and concepts of education can vary among different individuals. Everyone is given the same privilege to access education, regardless of age, financial status, or economic resources. As time progresses, education plays an important role in everything in human life. For some people, education is meant as a tool to make the nation's life more intelligent, for other people education is a step in improving their standard of living.

In this era of increasingly advanced development, Early Childhood Education should become one of the focuses in the world of education. As stated in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 7 of 2022 concerning Content Standards for Early Childhood Education, Basic Education Levels, and Secondary Education Levels in article 1 point 4 explains that Early Childhood Education, known as PAUD, is a program teaching provided to children from birth to six years of age. The aim is to provide educational stimuli that assist children in their physical and spiritual growth, ensuring they are equipped for the next stage of learning.

Social emotionality has independence as an important aspect of it. Independence in early childhood is required to be developed and stimulated well to achieve the desired results. Optimally developing independence is a must in the development of social-emotional aspects in early childhood. The child's attitude and readiness in the future is a consideration for the child. Lack of development of independent abilities in children will make it difficult for children to adapt and overcome simple problems within themselves, and this will make children constantly depend on other people. Developing independence in children requires the contribution of all parties around the child such as parents, family, those closest to the child, and educators at school.

Talking about social emotionality, in this case, independence in early childhood, the immediate environment, and the people around them greatly influence this ability. Children need to be given the freedom to express themselves and explore in try new things to instill a sense of self-confidence in young children that children are capable of doing new things. Having the ability to be independent in early childhood will trigger the child to explore these things which will make the child confident in himself to be able to do things that are new to him.

The problem found was in group B with an age range of 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School in the form of children's lack of independent abilities. This problem can be seen when at the beginning of the snack time activity the children still need help from the teacher to help them prepare their eating utensils after they are finished the children still need the teacher's help to help them tidy up their eating utensils. In other activities, such as when a child has finished playing with a toy, the child still cannot take the initiative to tidy up the toys he has used, the child tends to immediately run towards something else without tidying up the toys the child has used. In this case, it seems that the child still needs advice and reminders from the teacher so that the child

cleans up his eating utensils and tidy up the toys that the child has just played with.

Any learning and good habits implemented at school are not enough to develop independent abilities in young children, apart from these things, they require appropriate special stimulation to develop children's independence. In response to this, the use of technology can be used as a means of facilitating the development of children's independent abilities. Through rapidly developing technology, learning can be supported and the stimulus provided will be optimal. Learning using technology can be a means of delivering learning communication between teachers and children. In line with this, animated film media which is close to technology can be applied to growing and developing independence in children aged 5-6 years.

Using animated film learning media is one solution for interesting learning and provides variety and a breath of fresh air when children start to get bored. One of the advantages or advantages of using films in learning is that through films or videos, you can depict a suitable process and can be watched repeatedly when you feel the need to replay it.

The results of research conducted by Lisefti Fatimah et al (2020) show that there is a positive relationship between independence in early childhood and the activities carried out by children after the use of animated film media. In the research conducted, researchers used the animated film "Nusa and Rara" owned by The Little Giant Studio at RA Mubarakah Firrizqi Ciamis.

Based on the research background described above, it is hoped that the use of animated film media can instill the value of independence in young children. Based on the explanation above, the author is interested in taking the research title "The Influence of Animated Film Media on the Independence of Group B Children Aged 5-6 Years in TK Prestige Bilingual School".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Independence in Early Childhood

Syamsu Yusuf (Susanto, 2017) states that independence is a characteristic found in a healthy personality, and a person's independence can be seen from the way they think and act, can make their own decisions, can position themselves constructively by the norms that apply in the environment surroundings. Based on the opinions of several experts, it can be concluded that independence is a person's ability to use their abilities to do things themselves without depending on other people.

The definition from the National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAEYC) in (Susanto) states that children in the age range 0-8 are considered early childhood. According to the Subdirector of Early Childhood Education (PAUD), a child is considered to be in early childhood when he is between zero and six years old (0-6), which indicates that the range of early childhood is limited until the child completes his childhood. Early childhood children are born with their characteristics and specialties, with potential that is different from other children, with characteristics and interests that are of course also different from other children. During this period,

children also experience every stage of growth and development, starting from the psychological and mental levels, which are the fastest compared to others.

Independence is closely related to discipline in early childhood, starting from time discipline, discipline in how to dress, discipline in putting back items that have been used, and many other things. According to Wiyani (Wiyani, 2013), the following are several characteristics of independence in early childhood, namely children can choose their path, dare to decide something of their wishes, are responsible for the consequences of their choices, have self-confidence, and have creative and innovative attitude. , not dependent on other people, and can adapt to the environment.

Animation Film Learning Media

Media has a close relationship with the world of education. Its main function is as a bridge between two parties involved in the learning process. Media can deliver messages and learning objectives more clearly and appropriately. Not only communicating verbally, the media has an important role in transmitting learning material and educational values. According to Gerlach and Ely as quoted in Arsyad (2013), media can be defined as anything, be it humans, materials, or events that stimulate students' conditions so that they can acquire knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

Utilizing the use of learning media can influence the learning outcomes obtained by children, through the use of learning media it can have a positive influence on children in learning. Learning media is not only for channeling and conveying information to students but also for providing new ideas, insights, and knowledge. Learning media makes learning more varied and interesting when applied to students.

Films are included in the type of audiovisual media because films can contain information and knowledge through visual form as well as audio or sound. Films are usually known for their entertainment purposes, but animated films can also serve as documentation media and can be educational tools. According to Danim (2010), educational films used with children are considered effective as aids in education, films shown in front of children must also have an appropriate relationship to the learning topic being discussed. Film is a moving (living) image, film is also often called a movie.

According to Arsyad (2013), films also have weaknesses and strengths, namely:

1. Advantages of Using Film Media

a. Provide new experiences

The use of film media will provide new learning experiences for students to experience. These experiences can fill gaps in children's activities so that they can provide new enthusiasm, new insights, and new learning experiences. Children's interest in new things will pave the way for children to understand the material being discussed. The use of film media can replace real objects that might be very difficult to obtain in similar objects or situations, so films can replace that role. For example, regarding natural phenomena that cannot be known,

such as the process by which a volcano erupts and the process by which rain occurs.

b. Can be learned repeatedly

Films can replace real objects in children's learning, although not completely, but with animated films they can provide a similar picture of the shape of these real objects. Films can depict a process or event accurately so that it can be viewed or played continuously when necessary as an effort to improve learning.

c. Instilling affectional values in children

Instilling affective values in early childhood can be implemented indirectly. Not only can it provide new experiences and increase learning motivation in children, but film media can also instill attitudes and other affective aspects. Through the film media that children see and hear, it can be a trigger for children to improve good things about themselves. For example, an educational film that shows how important it is to throw rubbish in its place will make children aware of this.

d. Contains positive values

Some films have a moral message contained in them. The moral messages and positive values that exist will provide moral knowledge that can be applied to children in their daily lives. Giving or showing films repeatedly will instill good habits in children, so that these will stick with the child until the child grows up in the future.

e. Gives knowledge to be alert

The use of film media can present events that children should not go through and children should not touch these things because they are considered dangerous. For example, when children are close to fire and play with this object.

f. Can be given to various groups

Films can be shown to various types of groups in society, whether small groups large groups in society, or also heterogeneous groups or individual individuals.

g. Combining events at several times

Through advances in film technology and frame-by-frame shooting techniques, films whose original duration took days can be shown on film with a period of just one or two minutes. For example, the process of flower blooming starts from the flower bud developing into a flower that blooms.

2. Weaknesses of using film media

a. The cost of making a film is expensive

Film media is one of the media that takes advantage of technological advances. Films usually require a lot of money, and the energy of many people and take a long time in the making process. When making a film, several parts of the frame are usually combined into one unit to form a film that is worthy of viewing. This is the process of making which requires a long time and using sophisticated supporting equipment.

b. Not adapting to students' abilities

Films are made by combining several frames so that they can move continuously according to each part of the film. Students' learning abilities vary, so this is why not all children who see the film being shown can follow the information in the film being shown.

c. The available films are not suitable for learning

Not all of the films available support learning or are appropriate to the learning theme being conveyed. For this reason, the film must adapt the film to the theme that wants to be developed in the learning that is being carried out.

Animated films can be a media choice to support the achievement of learning objectives. Animated films used in the learning and teaching process can influence and improve aspects of children's affection because animated films contain visuals about an event that is depicted through interesting roles according to the available story. Stories depicted through characters that attract children are one of the main points why animated films can develop independence in children, because children are individuals who tend to be interested in sounds and visuals, for this reason animated films can be suitable for children who are shown them. Children tend to see directly how appropriate visuals are in increasing independent abilities in early childhood.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses a quantitative type of research. This research uses an experimental method, the experimental method is a quantitative research method used to determine the effect of independent variables (treatment) on dependent treatment (results) under controlled conditions.

The place where this research was carried out was at TK Prestige Bilingual School which is located on Street of Bromo Number. 224, Binjai, Medan Denai District, Medan City, North Sumatra. The research implementation time will last for 2 months, starting from June to August.

In this study, the population used was all group B students aged 5-6 years old at TK Prestige Bilingual School Academic Year 2022/2023 with 15 students

in one class. The sampling technique used in this research was using a cluster sampling technique using 15 samples.

The research procedures used in this research are the pre-field stage, field activity stage, and final research stage. This research uses a research design of the Equivalent Time Samples Design type, in this type of design, the treatment is applied not just once but repeatedly, interspersed with periods where no treatment is given.

This research uses a non-test instrument in the form of direct observation regarding the independent abilities of early childhood children aged 5-6 years in group B at TK Prestige Bilingual School. Observation data in the form of direct observations will contain several descriptors that suit the needs of research data collection.

The data analysis technique used in this research uses inferential statistical techniques. Inferential techniques are statistics used to analyze sample data and the results will be generalized or inferred to the population from which the sample was taken (Gunawan, 2013). Nonparametric statistics will be applied to this research considering that the samples used in this research are less than 30 samples.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing the research hypothesis was carried out using inferential statistics with the Wilcoxon test with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, taking into account treated and untreated data. If you get $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected and vice versa. If $t_{count} > t_{table}$ then the hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is an influence of the use of animated films on the independence of children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School.

Hypothesis testing is carried out using the signed rank test (Wilcoxon signed test).

Table 1. Hypothesis Test Calculation Results Given Treatment and No Treatment

		Ranks		
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
After Before	Negative Ranks	0 ^a	.00	.00
	Positive Ranks	15 ^b	8.00	120.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	15		
a. After < Before b. After > Before c. After = Before				

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Results

- Based on the table above, the ranking interpretation is as follows:
- Negative ranks or the difference (negative) between before being given treatment and after being given treatment (before using animated film media and after using animated film media) is 0, both in the N value, Mean Rank, and Sum Ranks. The value 0 in the Negative Ranks table indicates there is no decrease or reduction in the total of 15 data.
 - Positive ranks or positive differences (increases) before being given treatment and after being given treatment, is that there are 15 positive data (N), which means that the 15 students experienced an increase in their scores from a treatment value of 2 to a value without treatment of 2. The mean rank or average increase is 8.00. Meanwhile, the number of positive ranks or the sum of ranks is 120.00.
 - Ties is a security with a treatment value of 2 and no treatment of 2, and in the table, it can be seen that the value of ties is 0, so it can be said that there is no equal value between before being treated and after being treated.

Table 2. Test Statistics Results

Test Statistics	
	Treatment - No Treatment
Z	-3.520 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test b. Based on negative ranks.	

Source: SPSS 25 Processing Results

Based on the "Test Statistics" output, it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.000 is smaller than <0.05 , so it can be concluded that the "hypothesis is accepted" meaning that there is a significant difference in results between before and after being treated with animated films, so it can also be concluded that "there is an influence of the use of film media animation towards the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School".

DISCUSSION

The research being discussed was carried out at TK Prestige Bilingual School with a sample size of 15 children. The data collection technique used in this research is an instrument that has been created based on research variables and indicators.

In analyzing the data, the author used a quantitative research method that was more systematic, planned, and structured from the beginning of the research to the end and was not influenced by conditions in the field. The independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at the TK Prestige Bilingual School still needs to be developed, because of this the author conducted research at the school using animated film media in learning activities carried out at the TK Prestige Bilingual School.

The average score given treatment for children's independence was 10.53 in the very good category, while not being treated for children's independence with a value of 9.13 in the very good category. Based on these scores, it shows that learning activities using animated film media can increase independence in group B children aged 5-6 years at the TK Prestige Bilingual School, as evidenced by the scores obtained for treatment and non-treatment.

Then, in testing the data hypothesis, the t_{count} value = 0.000 and t_{table} (with a significance level of 0.05), the t_{count} value is <0.05 , so the hypothesis is that there is a significant influence from the use of animated film media on the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years. at TK Prestige Bilingual School.

Based on the results of this data analysis, it can be said that the use of animated film media in the process of learning activities in developing independent abilities can have a significant effect. Therefore, repeated use of animated film media can provide stimulation in developing independence in children, because there are many sources of animated films specifically for children that are easy to access and use.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the research conducted, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence on the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School. From the results of data collection, the average score for children who were given the first treatment was 8.93 with a sample of 15 children and those who were not given the first treatment received an average score of 7.66 with a sample of 15 children. Then those who were given the second treatment got a score of 10.53 with a sample of 15 children and those who were not given the second treatment got a score of 9.13 with a sample of 15 children. Then, based on the results of hypothesis testing, the data obtained is a value of $t_{count} = 0.000$ and t_{table} (with a significance level of 0.05), the value of t_{count} is <0.05 so the hypothesis states that there is a significant influence on the use of animated film media on the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School. So it can be concluded that H_a is accepted so that it can be stated that "There is a significant influence from the use of animated film media on the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years at TK Prestige Bilingual School".

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions from the research results, the researcher proposed several suggestions addressed to various parties interested in the results of this research, including:

1. Educators must continue to innovate in developing learning activities that can help children develop independent abilities, such as using animated film media that is appropriate to the developmental achievements they want to develop in children.
2. For school principals, it is hoped that this research will be a basis for consideration in developing the independent abilities of group B children through the use of animated film media.
3. For children, it is hoped that through the medium of animated films, they can continue to improve children's independent abilities.
4. For future researchers who want to research further regarding the independence of group B children aged 5-6 years, it is hoped that they can carry out further research on the use of animated film media.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

For advanced research, we hope to be able to see other researchers using more ways to create animation media to support children's independence.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank everyone who was involved in writing this article, especially the principal and teachers as well as students at TK Prestige Bilingual School.

REFERENCES

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2010. *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta. PT Rineka Cipta
- Arsyad, Azhar. 2013. *Media Pembelajaran*. Jakarta. Rajawali Pers
- Chairilisyah, Daviq. (2019). Analisis Kemandirian Anak Usia Dini. *PAUD Lectura : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 3(1), 88-98.
- Danim, Sudarwan. 2010. *Media Komunikasi Pendidikan*. Jakarta. PT Bumi Aksara.

- Demillah, Airani. (2019). Peran Film Animasi Nussa dan Rara Dalam Meningkatkan Pemahaman Tentang Ajaran Islam Pada Pelajar SD. *Jurnal Interaksi*. 3(2), 106-115.
- Hutasuhut, A. R. S & Yaswinda. (2020). Analisis Pengaruh Film Nussa dan Rara Terhadap Empati Anak Usia Dini di Kota Padang. *Jurnal Pendidikan Tambusai*, 4(2), 1237-1246.
- Khadijah & Armanila. 2017. *Pemasalahan Anak Usia Dini*. Medan. Perdana Publishing
- Lestari, S. & Fathiyah, K. (2023). Analisis Pembelajaran dalam Meningkatkan Kemandirian Pada Anak Usia 5-6 Tahun. *Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 7(1), 398-405.
- Mashar, Riana. 2011. *Emosi Anak Usia Dini dan Strategi Pengembangannya*. Jakarta. Prenadamedia Group
- Noor, Juliansyah. 2011. *Metodologi Penelitian: Skripsi, Tesis, Disertasi, dan Karya Ilmiah*. Jakarta. Prenada Media Group
- Putra, Ricky dan Ahmad. 2022. *Pengantar Dasar Perencanaan dan Pembuatan Film Animasi*. Yogyakarta. Penerbit Andi
- Sukiman. 2019. *Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran*. Jakarta. Rajawali Pers
- Sugiyono. 2019. *Metode Penelitian*. Bandung. Alfabeta
- Suryana & Dadan. 2018. *Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini Stimulasi dan Aspek Perkembangan Anak*. Jakarta. Prenadamedia Group

Fauziah, Kamtini

Susanto, Ahmad. 2017. Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini (Konsep dan Teori). Jakarta. PT Bumi Aksara.

Wiyani, Novan. 2013. Bina Karakter Anak Usia Dini. Yogyakarta. Ar-Ruzz Media

Yus, Anita. 2011. Model Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini. Jakarta. Prenadamedia Group

Yus, Anita. 2011. Penilaian Perkembangan Belajar Anak Taman Kanak-Kanak. Jakarta. Prenadamedia Group